

Universal Design for Learning (UDL1) and Living (UDL2) in Virtual Reality-based Treatments for Children with Autism

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ABSTRACT

Interest in virtual reality (VR) technology for special education is growing steadily. In Singapore, it has begun to play a crucial role in the Special Education for Autism (SEA), which calls for a more focused, systematically structured framework to cater to such students' needs. As autism is a syndrome with co-morbid subtypes and different degrees of severity, there is a need for a Universal Design for both learning (UDL1) and living (UDL2) to meet all the various needs and demands of these students. Adapted from the Response to Intervention (RtI) initiative first introduced under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act of 2004 (IDEA) in the United States, the SEA framework is divided into three treatment levels which cover all core autism treatment practices, supplemental autism treatments, and individually customized autism treatments. The focus of this paper is to examine the application of UDL1 and UDL2 features in virtual reality-based autism treatments (VRAT) within the framework of contextual teaching and learning (CTL) through reflective questioning.

Categories and Subject Descriptors

D.2.1 [Software Engineering]: Requirements/Specifications – Methodologies

D.2.10 [Software Engineering]: Design – Methodologies, Representation

D.2.12 [Software Engineering]: Interoperability – Data mapping

D.2.13 [Software Engineering]: Reusable Software– Reuse models.

K.3.1 [Computing Milieux]: Computer uses in Education – collaborative learning, computer-assisted instruction.

General Terms

Algorithms, Management, Documentation, Performance, Design, Experimentation, Human Factors, Languages, Theory.

Keywords

autism, special education, virtual dolphins, Universal Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

With better understanding of autism, a new Special Education for Autism (SEA) framework, adapted from the Response to Intervention (RtI) initiative [1], is developed to provide adaptive or differentiated instruction to students with autism to manage their challenges that limit or impair their learning and behavior, to meet their needs and maximize their potential. Its ultimate goal is to achieve a high-quality treatment for all students with autism, and, if required, provide more intensive, specialized and structured treatment to match student need, monitor progress to ensure that these students succeed both academically and behaviorally. Hence, it is necessary to focus on instruction and training and also highlight how other variables (e.g., policies on special education) beyond instruction/training are essential to support students' success. Like the RtI structure, the SEA framework has three treatment levels (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Framework of Special Education for Autism (SEA)

The level 1 treatment uses research-based core autism treatment for learning and behavior, e.g., structured instruction and learning environment and behavior modification [2]. The level 2 supplemental autism treatments (e.g., special diet), administered by professionals engaged in autism research, concern targeted, research-based interventions, offered in rapid response to students in need of supplemental intervention [2]. The level 3 intensive customized autism treatments involves a trans-disciplinary team of specialists for students who need them most, based on assessments and performance data [2].

Although SEA covers a wide range of conventional as well as complementary and alternative autism treatments, many of them lack evidences of efficacy (e.g., facilitated communication) or may have side effects (e.g., chelation therapy). Hence, it is very

important to identify scientifically validated autism treatments that can offer an effective early intervention program. The authors of this paper have chosen to focus on virtual reality-based autism treatments (VRAT), a level 2 treatment, where teachers and parents play the role of a mediator.

2. VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY

2.1 VR-based Autism Treatment (VRAT)

Interest in VR technology within the special education community has been growing rapidly since the beginning of the new millennium. Today, VR application research has offered more opportunities and a wider scope for developing innovative autism treatment [3][4]. Findings from these studies (e.g., [5][6]) suggested the effectiveness of VR-based behavioral training for students with autism for obvious reasons: firstly, students with autism like computerized games; secondly, their intact and even superior skill in systematizing empowers their learning and comprehension of predictable artifacts involved in playing the VR games; and thirdly, there are repeating movements or sequences which allows gradual building up of perception and understanding of construct of game.

The success of VRAT concerns two aspects important to students with autism: learning and living. How accessible VRAT is to students with autism of all co-morbid subtypes and varying degrees of severity can be attained through use of proactive instructional design, instructional strategies, and technology that supports multi-representation of knowledge, engagement, and expression of understanding [2]. This has been termed as Universal Design for Learning (UDL1). In addition, how successful VRAT prepares these students for independent and fulfilling lives when they enter adulthood has been termed as Universal Design for Living (UDL2). Its goal puts a high value on both diversity and inclusiveness [7] (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. UDL1 and UDL2 within the CTL Framework

2.2 Universal Design (UD) for VRAT

Universal Design (UD) is a paradigm where individuals of all abilities are included in the intended user population of an application, be it a product, service or environment [7]. Today, UD literature has extended to cover information design (education and Internet), product design (consumer and transportation), and place design (interior, exterior/landscapes and structure) [7].

In developing VRAT with UD features, many factors have to be considered to ensure that its accessibility to all students with autism of co-morbid subtypes and varying degrees of severity. In

addition, VRAT can be a product (e.g., VR games), a service (i.e., VR-assisted treatment), and an environment (e.g., virtual classroom). It also involves the process and principles of UD for Learning (UDL1) and Living (UDL2) placed within the framework of contextual teaching and learning (CTL) [8] embedded in four curriculum orientations: academic rationalism, development of cognitive, conative and affective processes [9], personal relevance, and social adaptation/reconstruction [10] (see Figure 2).

3. CONTEXTUAL TEACHING AND LEARNING IN VRAT

The term contextual teaching and learning (CTL) assumes that teaching and learning are context-driven [10] and views the learning environment, where teaching and learning take place, as existing both within and outside the school setting. According to Berns and Erickson [8], CTL is defined as “a conception of teaching and learning that helps teachers relate subject matter content to real world situations and motivates students to make connections between knowledge and its applications to their lives as family members, citizens, and workers” (para.3).

When VRAT is placed within the CTL framework, the following characteristics must be considered in relation to the usefulness of its application as an educational/treatment tool:

1. To connect content to the experiences of these students with autism;
2. To engage students with autism in active learning;
3. To enable students with autism to have some opportunities to direct their own learning as and when they are ready or opportunities become available;
4. To encourage the construction of personal meanings from a student with autism and collective experiences if possible;
5. To assess the attainment of outcomes within an authentic situation and allowing for the interpretation of multiple meanings from a single experience, which has to be structured for the student with autism; and
6. To identify contexts that are appropriate developmentally to the student with autism and this includes the application of Universal Design for Learning (UDL1) and Living (UDL2).

Moreover, the CTL framework is built on four core educational orientations that have to be incorporated into VRAT to make it a viable educational tool for treating students with autism. The first orientation is academic rationalism. It concerns essential content knowledge and skills to be imparted in VRAT (e.g., basic language concepts and skills needed for communication). The second orientation covers the development of cognitive, conative and affective processes [9]. It concerns the total development of the student mind through the processes that acquire information and skills needed to think and learn (cognition), the instinct to carry out self-determined acts to achieve a targeted end (conation), and the ability to attribute mental states to oneself and others and to understand that others have beliefs, desires and intentions that are different from one’s own (affect). This is known as the theory of mind [9]. Students with autism have a faulty theory of mind and also exhibit stereotyped behavior. Moreover, their ability to communicate and interact socially is impaired, too. The third orientation concerns learning that must be of personal relevance to a student with autism. The student

constantly struggles to make meaning from his experiences, construct knowledge from the meanings he has created, and then socially negotiate his personal meanings and knowledge with others, and inevitably become an informed, active citizen [10]. Current VRAT studies cover more on teaching joint attention and communication skills [11], social understanding [12], and counterfactual imagination in play [13]. More can be done to empower these students by making VR applications relevant to their daily practical needs. The last orientation refers to the societal adaptation/reconstruction. It suggests that VRAT should provide experiences enabling students with autism to acquire the necessary concepts and skills to succeed in life. According to Chiarelott [10], societal reconstruction addresses the current social needs and also stresses the essence of a learner as a change agent. Given the challenges a student with autism faces and the current societal state, the only constant is change. Those working with such students must recognize the need for and direction of change through advocacy and/or activism to improve their lives. Adaptation also involves change both within oneself and within the environment, be it virtual or physical. For VRAT to succeed in attaining what it has been designed to do, change cannot be avoided. VRAT has to be modified and updated to adapt to the needs of these students whose patterns of autism change as they grow older or mature [14].

These four core orientations contribute to the CTL design by showing how the content drawn from academic rationalism and the context of societal adaptation/reconstruction are connected via the development of cognitive, conative and affective processes with personal relevance to students with autism. On the one hand, the content can be fully appreciated by students with autism if UDL1 features are implemented in pedagogy and resources. On the other hand, the context has to be barrier-free and accessible if UDL2 comes into picture. To understand the UDL1/UDL2 application in VRAT, there is a need to know both the process and principles of Universal Design (UD) in VRAT.

4. Universal Design (UD) in VRAT

The process of UD involves the following sequence of operational steps: identify the application (i.e., product, service and/or environment) and in this case, it is VRAT→define the population of VRAT users→involve all VRAT users with diverse traits→adopt guidelines or standards within the field of the VRAT specific application→plan for accommodations from VRAT users for whom the design of VRAT does not automatically provide access→train and support VRAT users and other stakeholders→evaluate VRAT based on feedback from VRAT users.

VRAT as a product (e.g., VR games), a service (i.e., VRAT using avatars to interact with users) or an environment (i.e., the virtual classroom) [7][11] embraced the following seven UD principles:

Equitable use: Understanding autism is essential when planning an appropriate VRAT curriculum embracing UDL1 features. It must be appealing to all students regardless of their co-morbid subtypes and degrees of severity. Moreover, what is taught in UDL1 must be meaningful and practical when it is transferred to UDL2 for daily living activities.

Flexible use: Autistic pattern changes over time. Hence, VRAT must be flexible to meet the changing needs of these students. It must also provide multiple channels to meet their different

interests and learning styles to express themselves with respect to communication, measurement and engagement that can motivate them to pursue and maintain on-task with VRAT material.

Simplicity and intuitive use: Studies have suggested that students with autism tend to be techno-savvy and love technological gadgets [5][15]. VRAT offers just that and it is easy to manage for them. However, the task structure of VRAT should be appropriate in order to support different unique learning styles of students with autism and intelligences.

Perceptibility: Students with autism who have sensory challenges need to have their sensory profiles established so that appropriate VR environments can be created, utilizing multiple modes of information presentation to represent concepts, ideas, and data to enable students with autism to comprehend the essential concepts presented by the different sensory modes [16].

Tolerance for error: VRAT should not cause students with autism to become easily confused and anxious, especially if they do not know how to do a task or transfer what they have learnt to their daily living activities lest they suffer a meltdown.

Low physical/mental effort: VRAT should be ergonomically sound. Its physical/mental demands must be within acceptable cognitive, conative, affective and sensory limits for all students with autism of co-morbid subtypes and varying degrees of severity. Although most students with autism can remain on-task for a long time, they do display certain level of threshold, in terms of sensory hyper-responsivity or hypo-responsivity, for tasks involving multi-sensory stimuli (e.g., VR-based games).

Size and space for use: This is not an issue in VRAT as virtual size and space can be easily created. However, not all students with autism can work together as a group. Many work better alone or in pairs. It is also easier for the teacher to manage them should any child display off-task behavior.

4.1 UD for Learning (UDL1) in VRAT

In UDL1 for VRAT, the ability of a student with autism to learn directly through experience depends on the range and complexity of the experiences being offered. These experiences may be restricted due to the limited real-world artifacts that a physical classroom setting can provide. Besides, there are also certain cognitive, conative and affective difficulties faced by these students when they are taken out of their classroom or school. In VRAT, such problems can be avoided.

4.2 UD for Living (UDL2) in VRAT

In UDL2 for VRAT, application (e.g., language concepts and social skills acquired in daily living routine) allows students with autism to practice in different virtual learning scenarios (e.g., buying food at the school canteen), experience things that they are normally unaware, transfer to real places of different situations, and interact with virtual or real people. Moreover, UDL2 for these students also needs to consider keeping their living environment stable and predictable to support their living habits and activities. While the environment for living presents unique requirements for stability and predictability, a common theme across all environments is the need to reduce the inherent variability or common cause of the processes or activities that occur in it [16].

4.3 UDL1 and UDL2 Guiding Questions

The guiding questions on VRAT to reflect on its respective seven UDL1 and UDL2 features can be summed up in the table below:

UD Principles	UDL1	UDL2
Equitable use	Is VRAT useful to students with autism of co-morbidities and varying degrees of severity	
	to acquire essential concepts and social skills?	able to meet the daily living needs of these students?
Flexible use	Basing on individualized preferences and varied abilities of students with autism, does VRAT accommodate	
	different learning styles for certain activities?	a wide range of daily living needs (e.g., choosing a dress)?
Simplicity & intuitive use	Regardless of the student's experience, intellect, knowledge, language skills, or current concentration level, is VRAT	
	easy to understand and apply in the learning concepts or acquiring social skills?	apply and practical enough to meet the daily living needs (e.g., to follow systematic steps to complete a task)?
Perceptibility	To all students with autism regardless of their ambient conditions or sensory abilities, is VRAT in providing essential information for	
	learning concepts and social skills?	on practical applications (e.g., provision of audio instruction and pictorial cues to complete a task)?
Tolerance for error	Does VRAT allow error to happen as a result of accidental or unintended wrong use so as to reduce hazards and the adverse consequences of the actions	
	during learning of concepts or social skills?	encountered in daily living routine (e.g., took the wrong bus to school and knows what to do next)?
Least physical or mental effort required	Can VRAT be used efficiently, comfortably, and with a minimum of physical or mental fatigue	
	during learning of concepts and social skills?	daily living routine?
Size & space for use	Does VRAT provide size and space for the students regardless of body size, posture, or mobility	
	during the learning activities	when transferring what is learnt to apply in different experiential situations?

5. CONCLUSION

This paper explicates the authors' conceived theoretical structure of UDL1 and UDL2 as applied to students with autism in the CTL framework of VRAT incorporating four core educational orientations. The thinking and the principles behind the requirements, issues and challenges are discussed with the authors' proposal of the need to reach an effective balance that is to be derived from practical use with the spectrum of diverse needs evident in students with autism.

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